

The Study of the Relationship among Team Member Exchange Relationship, Trust and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

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Abstract: The society is a group composed of people and other people's activities. Organizational citizenship behavior has become a key factor that can restrict the survival and development of various social organizations. This study aims to explore the relationship among team member exchange relationship, trust and organizational citizenship behavior. Through quantitative research, the students of A university were surveyed, of which 208 valid questionnaires were collected. The study found that team member exchange relationship has the significant positive relationship with organizational citizenship behavior; cognitive trust has a partial mediating effect and the full mediating effect on the relationship among intrinsic interests, extrinsic interests and helping behavior; affective trust has a full mediating effect on the relationship between team member exchange relationship and organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: Team member exchange relationship, Trust, Organizational citizenship behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

When college students enter university, students also enter a small society. Student organizations are a platform for college students to grow and exercise their abilities. Good relationships within the team and improve efficiency in cooperation is related to the development of the organization (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). Friendly relationships among team members are conducive to the sustainable and healthy development of student organizations. At this time, positive organizational citizenship behavior can eliminate the negative impact of various selfish behaviors (De Los Ríos & Oseguera, 2023). The behaviors that focus on the interests of the entire organization or team are a type of citizenship behavior (Xu & Wang, 2020). For team members, improving organizational citizenship behavior is great significant to the survival and development of student organizations. Trust is the recognition and trust of other members in their own abilities. Good team relationships are conducive to mutual understanding among members and promote the establishment of trust.

Team member exchange relationships are positively correlated with organizational citizenship behavior (Rashid, Shahab, Zahur & Akhtar, 2021). Employees have a high sense of trust in the organization, which also show that the higher the degree of trust in the organization. It is helpful to improve organizational citizenship behavior (Soelton, 2023). Based on the above research viewpoints, this study would take the student organization of A University as the survey object, and use quantitative research in the form of questionnaire survey to explore the relationship between team member exchange relationship and organizational citizenship behavior and examine the mediating role of trust in the relationship.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Team member exchange relationship

In the past, the research usually focused on corporate leader-member exchange relationships, and relatively lacked on student organizations. The affairs or activities of college student organizations have invisibly prompted students to cultivate their leadership skills in team member cooperation. Therefore, it is important to establish a good team exchange relationship.

Achhnani and Gupta (2022) pointed out a good member exchange relationship would enable an individual to gain the respect and cooperation of colleagues, who will give him feedback on his work, and also form a reciprocal relationship in knowledge sharing and feedback interactions (Seers, Petty & Cashman, 1995). Therefore, this study believes that the team member exchange relationship is a mutual benefit process between each other, which is based on perception. Team members would perceive the goodwill of the team and pass on the good intention to form a friendly and mutually supportive team atmosphere. Good team relationships would make the team work better.

Murphy (2003) proposed that a good exchange relationship would lead to good team performance and generate extra efforts, even without additional rewards. Guo (2017) believed that members would exchange internal and external interests when they exchange. The internal interest exchange is mutual trust, acceptance and support between members, while external interest exchange refers to the help from other members. Based on previous research, this study would adopt Guo's definition of exchange relationship among team members, and divide team exchange relationship into two dimensions: internal interest and external interest.

2. Organizational citizenship behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior is a spontaneous behavior that goes beyond work roles and promotes the achievement of work goals. Organ (1988) believed that organizational citizenship behavior is an individual behavior that comes from the employees' consciousness and the personal willing, rather than institutional or other constraints. Bachrach (2007) believed that organizational citizenship behavior plays an important role in performance evaluation. Organizational citizenship behavior includes helpful behavior and civic morality. Robbins (1990) believed that organizational citizenship behavior could help team members to do things spontaneously and thereby avoid negative conflicts. The organizational citizenship behavior is beneficial to the organization (Smith, Organ & Near, 1983).

Smith et al. (1983) constructed a two-dimensional model of organizational citizenship behavior: general compliance and altruistic behavior. The former emphasized that individuals comply with disciplinary norms, and the latter refers to individuals actively help other members of the organization. Coleman & Borman (2000) divided organizational citizenship behavior into three dimensions: (1) Altruistic, which refers to behaviors that directly help members of the organization and thus benefit the organization. (2) Pro-organizational, which refers to behaviors that directly help the organization. (3) Citizenship performance in work tasks refers to the behavior of organizational members who take the initiative to participate or provide additional help in their duties. Based on previous research, this study defines organizational citizenship behavior as helping behavior and civic morality towards the team. Helping behavior refers to the actions that team members are willing to take to help team members solve work-related problems. Civic morality refers to the behavior of team members who participate responsibly in organizational life.

3. Trust

Trust is a psychological intention that occurs when people gradually recognize whether the other party is reliable through communication in various aspects such as text, words, or behavior during interpersonal interaction. Chang, Cheung, & Tang (2013) believe that trust is a psychological state that allows the parties to accept the other party's intentions and behaviors and give the other party positive expectations. It has a positive predictive effect on the behavior of others in the team. Everyone expects to be treated sincerely and will also have positive feedback and will return the other party's trust[28], thereby performing behaviors that are beneficial to the other party. McAllister (1995) divides trust into cognitive and emotional trust. Emotional and cognitive trust determine whether interpersonal cooperation is smooth. Cognitive trust is objective in nature and uses rational and orderly procedures to judge whether an individual, group, or organization is reliable (Hansen, Morrow & Batista, 2002). Xu (2011) divides the basis of trust into three types, including: (1) rational analysis, using rationality to evaluate the behavior of others and evaluate the consequences of their behavior. (2) Obtain relevant information from long-term interactions with others, and use it to predict other people's behavior, thereby establishing and maintaining a trusting relationship. (3) Emotional identification comes from the long-term and in-depth understanding of the two parties' knowledge and values, and emotional attachment to each other.

This study divides trust into cognitive trust and emotional trust. Cognitive trust is evaluated based on previous performance and reliability. The better the evaluation result, the higher the cognitive trust. Emotional trust is the emotional interaction between team members, which is reflected in the confidence that others can bring benefits to themselves. The more positive the emotional interaction, the higher the confidence level, and the higher the emotional trust shown.

4. The relationship between team member exchange relationship and organizational citizenship behavior

Social exchange theory analyzes the rewards and costs in social interaction, and benefits can be gained through exchange. Therefore, the social interaction process can be regarded as an exchange process, and the team member exchange relationship is also a behavior of exchange of rewards and costs among team members in the process of interaction. This exchange includes emotional exchange, information sharing, and role identification. Chen, Wang, Chang & Hu (2008) pointed out that team member exchange directly affects organizational citizenship behavior.

In summary, this study believes that there is a positive relationship between team member exchange relationship and organizational citizenship behavior. The individual members of a good team would feel the emotional connection by other members in a good exchange relationship, as well as the value and significance of being a team member. The good exchange relationship also makes members realize that they belong to this team and take behaviors to promote the team. When team members feel trusted, accepted and supported from other members at work, they would also take corresponding "repay" behaviors, actively help other members of the team and show responsible and proactive participation in team work. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypotheses:

H1: Team member exchange relationships have a significant positive impact on organizational citizenship behavior

H1-1: Extrinsic benefits have a significant positive impact on helping behavior

H1-2: Extrinsic benefits have a significant positive impact on civic morality

H1-3: Intrinsic benefits have a significant positive impact on helping behavior

H1-4: Intrinsic benefits have a significant positive impact on civic morality

5. The mediating effect of trust in team member exchange relationships and organizational citizenship behavior

Düger (2021) showed that the development of trust and exchange relationships between counselors and students is mutually reinforcing. Since the quality of team-member exchange relationships is affected by team members' mutual perceptions, when there is a high degree of trust perception between team members, it would be conducive to the establishment of high-quality exchange relationships. Secondly, Huang, Qiu, Yang, & Deng (2021) showed that when organizational members perceive each other's highly reliable and are willing to selflessly share work ideas or make constructive suggestions, it has a positive reinforcing effect on members' display of organizational citizenship behavior. This also means that when employees perceive highly trusted and respected, and realize that the organization pays more attention for them, and they would have a sense of obligation to return in order to maintain this trust relationship. Hansen (2002) also believes that the more trust there is between teams, the more willing they are to exert their potential in the team.

When team members perceive a high degree of goodwill from team members, it would prompt individual members to trust team members and form a team atmosphere of frankness and respect. When members encounter difficulties, they are willing to face them together, which would inspire them beyond the requirements of their work roles, automatically and spontaneously assist other members to complete their work. Therefore, a hypothesis is proposed.

H2: Trust mediates the relationship between team member exchange relationships and organizational citizenship behavior

H2-1: Cognitive trust mediates the relationship between external interests and helping behaviors

H2-2: Cognitive trust mediates the relationship between external interests and civic morality

H2-3: Cognitive trust mediates the relationship between intrinsic interests and helping behaviors

H2-4: Cognitive trust mediates the relationship between intrinsic interests and civic morality

H2-5: Emotional trust mediates the relationship between external interests and helping behaviors

H2-6: Emotional trust mediates the relationship between external interests and civic morality

H2-7: Emotional trust mediates the relationship between intrinsic interests and helping behaviors

H2-8: Emotional trust mediates the relationship between intrinsic interests and civic morality

III. RESEARCH METHODS

1. Research framework

Based on the purpose and the review of previous papers, this study proposes a research framework, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research framework

2. Research Methods

This study would use paper questionnaires and online questionnaires to conduct a quantitative survey of students for A University, obtain samples of student organizations about team member exchange relationships, trust and organizational citizenship behavior. This study uses the new version of SPSS and AMOS software to perform statistical analysis on the samples, such as regression analysis, Sobel analysis, etc.

IV. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

1. Descriptive statistics

This study adopts the convenience sampling method and takes students from A University as the subjects. 250 questionnaires were distributed and 250 questionnaires were collected, with a collection rate of 100%. After eliminating 42 invalid questionnaires, 208 valid questionnaires remained, with an efficiency of 83.2%. In this study, males accounted for 28.8% and females accounted for 71.2%. The data shows that the proportion of females is much greater than that of males; in terms of major distribution, the main subjects filled in are science and engineering and liberal arts, of which science and engineering accounted for 82.7% and liberal arts accounted for 13.9%; in terms of the distribution of students' origin, it can be seen that most of the students who filled in the questionnaire were from rural areas, of which urban areas accounted for 26.9% and rural areas accounted for 73.1%.

This study used the Harman single factor analysis method to conduct factor analysis on all the items in the scale. Without axis rotation, a total of 5 factors were extracted, and the explained variance of the first factor was 39.8% (less than 50%). Therefore, this study did not have the problem of common variation.

2. Measurement of variables

This study used the Likert five-point scoring method to score each item. All items were positive questions with scores of 1 to 5 respectively.

2.1 Reliability Analysis

There are 5 questions on intrinsic benefits, and the α value is 0.834; there are 4 questions on extrinsic benefits, and the α value is 0.793. There are 4 questions on cognitive trust, and the α value is 0.888; there are 4 questions on affective trust, and the α value is 0.812. The α value of the 7-question Helping Behavior Question is 0.878; the α value of the 3-question Civic Morality Question is 0.717.

In addition, the overall Cronbach's α coefficient shows that the scale has very good reliability, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

	Factor	Cronbach's α 值	Overall
Team member exchange relationships	Intrinsic benefits	0.834	0.88
	Extrinsic benefits	0.793	
Trust	Cognitive trust	0.888	0.897
	Emotional trust	0.812	
Organizational citizenship behavior	Helping behavior	0.878	0.897
	Civil morality	0.717	

2.2 Construct reliability and validity analysis

According to the classification of Hair et al (1998), the construct reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity of all variables were further tested.

As shown in Table 3, the component reliability of each variable is between 0.564 and 0.851 (>0.6) (Baron & Kenny, 1987). The average variation extraction of each variable is greater than 0.5, except for the variable civic morality, which is slightly less than 0.5 but within the acceptable range. The discriminant validity of each variable is between 0.689 and 0.816. Except for the last variable civic morality, which is slightly close to the correlation coefficient with other variables, the other variables exceed the correlation coefficient between the variable and other latent variables. The variables in this study have good construct reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity.

2.3 Correlation analysis

Intrinsic interests, extrinsic interests, cognitive trust and affective trust are significantly positively correlated ($r=0.557$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.561$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.683$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.613$, $p<0.001$). Similarly, cognitive trust and affective trust are also significantly positively correlated with helping behavior and civic morality ($r=0.485$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.578$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.349$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.525$, $p<0.001$). In addition, there is a significant positive correlation between the intrinsic interests and extrinsic interests in the exchange relationship between team members and helping behavior and civic morality ($r=0.452$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.433$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.440$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.408$, $p<0.001$).

In summary, the three variables are positively correlated with each other. Therefore, this study can further verify the influence relationship of the hypothesized relationship between the variables in the research model.

Table 3: Construct reliability , convergent validity and discriminant validity of variables

Latent variables	items	Standardized factor loadings	CR	AVE	Discriminant validity
Intrinsic benefits	IB1	0.713	0.838	0.509	0.713
	IB2	0.708			
	IB3	0.656			
	IB4	0.771			
	IB5	0.715			
Extrinsic benefits	EB1	0.592	0.799	0.501	0.708
	EB2	0.723			
	EB3	0.745			
	EB4	0.758			
Cognitive trust	CT1	0.795	0.888	0.666	0.816
	CT2	0.821			
	CT3	0.851			
	CT4	0.795			
Emotional trust	ET1	0.737	0.814	0.525	0.725
	ET2	0.764			
	ET3	0.779			
	ET4	0.603			
Helping behavior	HB1	0.778	0.879	0.512	0.716
	HB2	0.717			
	HB3	0.765			
	HB4	0.656			
	HB5	0.736			
	HB6	0.564			
	HB7	0.767			
Civil morality	CM1	0.792	0.728	0.475	0.689
	CM2	0.573			
	CM3	0.686			

2.4 Regression Analysis

From the correlation analysis, we know that there is a significant positive correlation between the three variables, which can be used for regression analysis. The direct relationship between the variables is analyzed by multiple regression analysis, and the mediating influence is analyzed by hierarchical regression analysis.

There is a significant positive correlation between the intrinsic interests and extrinsic interests in the exchange relationship between team members and the cognitive trust and emotional trust in trust ($\beta=0.310$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.352$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.484$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.286$, $P<0.001$)

Cognitive trust and affective trust have a significant positive relationship with helping behavior ($\beta=0.485$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.578$, $P<0.001$), while cognitive trust and affective trust have a significant positive relationship with civic morality ($\beta=0.349$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.525$, $P<0.001$).

The intrinsic benefits and extrinsic benefits in the exchange relationship of team members have a significant positive impact on helping behavior and civic morality in organizational citizenship behavior ($\beta=0.301$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.222$, $P<0.01$; $\beta=0.303$, $P<0.001$; $\beta=0.197$, $P<0.05$). Therefore, hypotheses H1-1, H1-2, H1-3, and H1-4 are established.

The results show that cognitive trust has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between intrinsic benefits and helping behavior; in addition, from Model 3, when cognitive trust is added, the regression coefficient of external benefits in the exchange relationship between team members changes from significant to insignificant ($\beta=0.222$, $P<0.01 \rightarrow \beta=0.111$, $P > 0.05$), which indicates that cognitive trust has a complete mediating effect on the relationship between external benefits and helping behavior. Therefore, assumptions H2-1 and H2-3 are established.

Comparison of the data between Model 2 and Model 4 shows that after adding emotional trust to Model 4 ($\beta=0.475$, $P<0.001$), the regression coefficients of intrinsic and extrinsic benefits in the exchange relationship between team members changed from significant to insignificant ($\beta=0.301$, $P<0.001 \rightarrow \beta=0.071$, $P>0.05$; $\beta=0.222$, $P<0.01 \rightarrow \beta=0.086$, $P>0.05$). This result indicates that emotional trust has a complete mediating effect on the relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic benefits and helping behavior. Therefore, hypotheses H2-5 and H2-7 are established.

From the data comparison of Model 2 and Model 3 in Table 5, it can be concluded that when cognitive trust in Model 3 is added ($\beta=0.112$, $P > 0.05$), this result indicates that cognitive trust does not mediate the relationship between intrinsic interests and extrinsic interests and civic morality. Although the three are related to each other, the exchange relationship between team members does not need to further affect civic morality in organizational citizenship behavior through cognitive trust. Therefore, assumptions H2-2 and H2-4 are not established.

Comparison of the data between Model 2 and Model 4 shows that after adding emotional trust in Model 4 ($\beta=0.393$, $P<0.001$), the regression coefficients of intrinsic and extrinsic interests in the exchange relationship between team members changed from significant to insignificant ($\beta=0.303$, $P<0.001 \rightarrow \beta=0.113$, $P>0.05$; $\beta=0.197$, $P<0.05 \rightarrow \beta=0.084$, $P>0.05$). This result indicates that emotional trust has a complete mediating effect on the relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic interests and civic morality. Therefore, hypotheses H2-6 and H2-8 are established.

This study uses the Sobel test to test the significance of the indirect effect of trust. The test results show that cognitive trust has a significant mediating effect on intrinsic interests and helping behavior ($z=3.63$, $z>1.96$) and extrinsic interests and helping behavior ($z=4.03$, $z>1.96$); affective trust has a significant mediating effect on intrinsic interests and helping behavior ($z=5.85$, $z>1.96$), extrinsic interests and helping behavior ($z=3.96$, $z>1.96$), intrinsic interests and civic morality ($z=5.56$, $z>1.96$), and extrinsic interests and civic morality ($z=3.86$, $z>1.96$).

V. CONCLUSION

The study found that team member exchange relationship has a significant positive relationship with organizational citizenship behavior; cognitive trust has a partial mediating effect and a full mediating effect on the relationship between intrinsic interests, extrinsic interests and helping behavior; affective trust has a full mediating effect on the relationship between team member exchange relationship and organizational citizenship behavior.

In student organizations, when team members feel the trust, acceptance and support from other team members or receive help or advice from other members during work, they will receive internal or external goodwill and pass on this goodwill. They will actively help other team members to do some behaviors that are beneficial to the team or get closer to the team (helping behavior), and are more willing to participate in organizational life responsibly (civic morality).

The trust that team members have in other members based on their previous work performance or the amount of ability they have, or the emotional exchange between members in the interaction, will increase the degree to which team members feel internal and external goodwill in the exchange relationship, thereby strengthening the civic behavior between team organizations.

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